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Comparative Evaluation of Biogas Production from Cow Dung, Neem Seed and Groundnut Shell

¹Haliru A. A., ¹Gado A. A. and ¹Umar A. B.

¹Kebbi University of Science and Technology, Aliero Kebbi. Nigeria.

¹Department of Physics. Kebbi University of Science and Technology, Aliero Kebbi. Nigeria

ABSTRACT

Biogas, a renewable energy source primarily composed of methane and carbon dioxide, is produced by the microbial breakdown of organic materials in the absence of oxygen. This study investigates the production of biogas through the anaerobic digestion of organic substrates, specifically focusing on three substrate combinations: Cow Dung alone, Cow Dung mixed with Neem seed, and Cow Dung mixed with Groundnut shell for maximizing biogas yield and to identify the optimal process parameters, such as temperature and pH, that enhance anaerobic digestion efficiency. The results of the experiments revealed that the combination of Cow Dung and Groundnut shell yielded the highest volume of biogas, producing 1.14 cm³, compared to 0.84 cm³ for the Cow Dung and Neem seed mixture and 0.64 cm³ for Cow Dung alone, respectively. The highest volume of biogas obtained from the combination of Cow Dung and Groundnut shell is attributed to the balanced Carbon-to-Nitrogen (C/N) ratio present in the Cow Dung and Groundnut shell combination, which is essential for supporting the growth of microorganisms responsible for breaking down organic matter efficiently during anaerobic digestion. The study's findings revealed that using these materials can provide a promising solution for waste management and sustainable energy production.

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CONTACT Haliru A. An Email: abubakargadoa@gmail.com

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural waste refers to the byproducts, residues, or unused materials generated during agricultural production, processing, and consumption activities (Abdul-Jabbar et al., 2024). These waste materials can originate from various stages of the agricultural supply chain, including cultivation, harvesting, post-harvest handling, processing, and distribution (Ummalya et al., 2024). Agricultural waste can be classified into several categories based on its source, composition, and characteristics. Crop residues are the parts of crops left in the field after harvesting, such as stalks, leaves, husks, and stems. Crop residues can be generated from cereal crops (e.g., wheat straw, rice husks), oilseed crops (e.g., soybean hulls), and other agricultural commodities (Adesina et al., 2024). Animal waste includes organic waste from livestock farming operations, such as manure, urine, and bedding materials (see Adesina et al., 2024 for more). Animal waste contains valuable nutrients like nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium, but it can also pose environmental challenges if not managed properly (Singhania et al., 2024). Food processing by-products are the residues generated during the processing of agricultural commodities into food, feed, or industrial products. Examples include fruit and vegetable peels, pulp, seeds, and trimmings from meat and poultry processing (Sindhu et al., 2024). The agro-industrial waste category encompasses raw materials from agricultural industries, “such as sawdust from lumber mills, bagasse from sugarcane processing, and spent grain from breweries” (Akpan et al., 2022). Packaging waste

materials used for agricultural products, including plastic bags, containers, crates, and packaging films, contribute to agricultural waste when disposed of improperly (Akpan et al., 2022).

Biogas is a renewable energy source produced through the anaerobic digestion of organic materials such as agricultural waste, municipal solid waste, sewage sludge, and organic residues from industrial processes (Shukla et al., 2023). This process involves microorganisms breaking down organic matter in the absence of oxygen, resulting in the production of biogas, primarily consisting of methane (CH_4) and carbon dioxide (CO_2), along with small amounts of other gases such as hydrogen sulfide (H_2S) and traces of water vapor (Babatunde et al., 2022). Biogas production from agricultural waste represents a sustainable and eco-friendly solution for addressing energy needs while simultaneously managing organic residues. As the global demand for renewable energy rises, optimising biogas production from agricultural waste emerges as a crucial avenue for achieving environmental and economic benefits. In 2016, Horváth and Kumar investigated that lignocellulose materials have been widely recognised for a considerable period as an alternative source of raw materials for producing environmentally friendly biofuels. These materials can produce solid fuels such as briquettes, liquid fuels like bioethanol, and gaseous fuels like biogas (Devendra et al., 2024). Extensive attention has been directed towards utilising agricultural residues, food waste, and energy crops to generate biofuels.

According to research on the biogas potential of eight aquatic weeds, salvinia and Ceratopteris produced biogas with a maximum yield of $0.2 \text{ m}^3 \text{ kg}^{-1}$. Subsequently, adding inoculums will keep pistia producing biogas for ten days (Hassan et al., 2022). The most significant amount of methane was produced when Borja et al. investigated waste tires' kinetic behavior for biogas production supported by microorganisms in an anaerobic environment. In a study conducted by Ferreira et al. (2024) on the process of producing biogas with Wolffia and lemma, the findings revealed that these two microorganisms, when grown in a slurry-fed digester containing Cow Dung, can be employed in conjunction with the manure to produce biogas. Under various circumstances, investigations into the dynamics of producing biogas from municipal waste have revealed encouraging results. Industries processing milk can use wastewater to produce biogas and bio-hydration (Hamadou et al., 2020). There have also been reports on the impact of pH, carbon-to-nitrogen ratio, and solid content on biogas production. A study was conducted to identify unique annual and perennial plants for biogas generation, and the results showed that the biogas produced was of a higher caliber (Perveen, 2024). This study aims to maximise biogas yield under ideal operating conditions and investigate the impact of producing biogas at a consistent, profitable, and effective rate utilising rice husk and sugarcane pulp (Honcharuk et al., 2024). The study of biogas production from agricultural waste is important for several reasons, encompassing environmental, economic, and energy-related considerations (Karthik et al.,

2024). The production of biogas derived from agricultural waste has the potential to significantly contribute to our collective knowledge in many ways. First and foremost, such research can significantly enhance our understanding of renewable energy production (Khalil, 2020). We can expand our understanding of sustainable energy by exploring the complexities of the biogas production procedure, specifically regarding agricultural waste (Kusmiyati et al., 2023). Biogas, which is mainly composed of methane, represents a green and enduring energy source.

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials Used in the Study

The materials used in this research are:

- Cow Dung (CD)
- Neem Seeds (NS)
- Groundnut Shells (GS)
- Water
- 3 biodigesters
- pH meter
- Thermometer
- Beakers
- measuring cylinder
- Water container
- Beam balance

Method

Three biodigesters, A, B, and C, are made and labeled for cow dung, cow dung with Neem seed, and cow dung with Groundnut shells, respectively.

Plate 1: Pictorial Representation of the Three Bio-Digester Sets

Digester A (Cow Dung)

Substrate Collection and Treatment

Fresh Cow Dung was collected from cattle farms. 4 kg of the Cow Dung was mixed with 1000 cm³ (1 liter) water to form a slurry. Larger particles of Cow Dung were chopped to increase surface area and facilitate microbial action during digestion. A 0.03g of yeast was added as a catalyst.

The Cow Dung slurry was fed into an anaerobic digester, a sealed tank where anaerobic bacteria decomposed the organic matter. To optimise microbial activity, the digester was maintained at a controlled temperature (mesophilic range of 30-40°C), with the pH measured at 7.12

Plate 2: Bio-Digester A Set Up

Retention Time

Retention time is the length of time that the substrate spends in the digester. The substrate remained in the biodigester for 7 days, and the subsequent measurements of the pH level, temperature, and biogas produced were recorded for five consecutive days.

Determination of Biogas Produced

The amount of biogas produced was determined using the water displacement method. This method measures a substance's volume by measuring the volume of water it displaces.

Plate 3: Bio-Digester A Water Displacement Method

A measuring cylinder was filled with water and then upside-down in a container containing water. A retort stand was used to hold the measuring cylinder. The gas hose from the biodigester was inserted into the measuring cylinder, and the initial water level in the cylinder was recorded.

The biogas was then allowed to flow from the biodigester to the cylinder, and since gas is less dense than water, the biogas accumulated at the top of the cylinder, causing a decrease in the water level. The new water level was recorded,

and the volume of the gas produced was calculated by subtracting the new water level from the initial water level. This method is based on Archimedes' principle, which states that "the volume of an object is equal to the volume of the fluid it displaces. A thermometer was used to determine the temperature.

Plate 4: Determination of Bio-Digester A Temperature

Digester B (Cow Dung and Neem Seed)

Substrate Collection and Treatment

Fresh Cow Dung was collected from cattle farms. 4 kg of the Cow Dung was mixed with 1000 cm³ (1 liter) water to form a slurry. Larger particles of Cow Dung were chopped to increase surface area and facilitate microbial action during digestion. Neem seeds were dried and pounded, and then 1 kg of the powder was used. A 0.03g of yeast was added as a catalyst. The slurry was fed into an anaerobic digester, a sealed tank where anaerobic bacteria decomposed the organic matter. The digester was maintained at a controlled temperature (mesophilic range of 30-40°C) to optimise microbial activity. The pH was measured as 6.20

Plate 5: Bio-Digester B Set Up

Retention Time

The substrate remained in the biodigester for seven days, and subsequent measurements of the pH level, temperature, and biogas produced were recorded for five consecutive days.

Determination of Biogas Produced

The amount of biogas produced was determined using the water displacement method. A measuring cylinder was filled with water and then upside-down in a container containing water. A retort stand was used to hold the measuring cylinder. The gas hose from the biodigester was inserted into the measuring cylinder, and the initial water level in the cylinder was recorded.

Plate 6: Bio-Digester B Water Displacement Method

The biogas was then allowed to flow from the biogas digester to the cylinder. Since gas is less dense than water, the biogas accumulated at the top of the cylinder, causing a decrease in the water level. The new water level was recorded, and the volume of the gas produced was calculated by subtracting the new water level from the initial water level. A thermometer was used to determine the temperature.

Plate 7: Determination of Bio-Digester B Temperature

Digester C (Cow Dung and Groundnut Shell)
Substrate Collection and Treatment

Fresh Cow Dung was collected from cattle farms. 4 kg of the Cow Dung was mixed with 1000 cm³ (1 liter) water to form a slurry. Larger particles of Cow Dung were chopped to increase surface area and facilitate microbial action during digestion. Groundnut shells were dried and pounded, and then 1 kg of the powder was used. A 0.03g of yeast was added as a catalyst. The Cow Dung and Groundnut shells were thoroughly mixed to create a homogeneous mixture. This ensures the even distribution of nutrients and enhances microbial access to substrates during digestion. The mixed slurry was transferred into an anaerobic digester. The digester was maintained at a controlled temperature of mesophilic temperatures (30-40°C) to optimise microbial activity. The pH was measured as 6.1. Anaerobic bacteria decomposed the organic materials in the Cow Dung and Groundnut shells, producing biogas as a metabolic byproduct.

Plate 8: Bio-Digester C Set Up

Retention Time

The substrate remained in the biogas digester for seven days, and subsequent measurements of the

pH level, temperature, and biogas produced were recorded for five consecutive days.

Determination of Biogas Produced

The amount of biogas produced was determined using the water displacement method. A measuring cylinder was filled with water and then put upside-down in a container containing water. A retort stand was used to hold the measuring cylinder. The gas hose from the biodigester was inserted into the measuring cylinder, and the initial water level in the cylinder was recorded. The biogas was then allowed to flow from the biodigester to the cylinder, and since gas is less dense than water, the biogas accumulated at the top of the cylinder, causing a decrease in the water level.

Plate 9: Bio-Digester C Water Displacement Method

The new water level was recorded, and the volume of the gas produced was calculated by subtracting the new water level from the initial water level. This method is based on Archimedes' principle, which states that "the volume of an object is equal to the volume of the fluid it

displaces. A thermometer was used to determine the temperature.

Plate 10: Determination of bio-digester C temperature

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

At the end of this research, biogas was obtained from cow dung, cow dung with Neem seed, and cow dung with Groundnut shell. Tables 1- 3 of this chapter tabulate the experimental results obtained.

Bio Digester A (Cow Dung)

Mass of Cow Dung: 04 kg

The volume of water used: 1000 cm³

Mass of biodigester (before adding substrate): 01 kg

Mass of biodigester (after adding substrate): 06 kg

Amount of yeast added: 0.03 kg

Temperature: 31°C

pH level: 7.12

Retention time: 7 days

TABLE 1: Bio-Digester A Measurements (Cow Dung)

S/N	Days	pH level	Temperature (°C)	Biogas produced (cm ³)	M ₁ (kg)	M ₂ (kg)
1	Day 1	7.08	32.2	0.5	6.50	6.00
2	Day 2	7.03	33.1	0.6	6.50	6.02
3	Day 3	6.98	34.1	0.6	6.60	6.00
4	Day 4	6.94	34.9	0.7	6.70	6.00
5	Day 5	6.90	35.6	0.8	6.80	6.00

Where M₁ = mass of biodigester before measuring biogas

M₂ = mass of biodigester after measuring biogas

Figure 1: Graphical Representation of Bio-Digester A (Cow Dung)

Bio Digester B (Cow Dung and Neem Seed)

Mass of Cow Dung: 04 kg

Mass of Neem seed: 01 kg

The volume of water used: 1000 cm³

Mass of biodigester (before adding substrate): 01 kg

Mass of biodigester (after adding substrate): 07 kg

Amount of yeast added: 0.03 kg

Temperature: 32 °c

pH level: 6.20

Retention time: 7 days

TABLE 2: Bio-Digester B Measurements (Cow Dung and Neem Seed)

S/N	Days	pH level	Temperature (°C)	Biogas produced (cm ³)	M ₁ (kg)	M ₂ (kg)
1	Day 1	6.18	33.5	0.8	7.80	7.00
2	Day 2	6.15	34.8	0.7	7.70	7.00
3	Day 3	6.12	35.9	0.8	7.80	7.00
4	Day 4	6.09	36.5	0.9	7.90	7.00
5	Day 5	6.06	37.1	1.0	8.00	7.00

Where M₁ = mass of biodigester before measuring biogas

M₂ = mass of biodigester after measuring biogas

Figure 2: Graphical Representation of Bio-Digester B (Cow Dung and Neem Seeds)

Bio Digester C (Cow Dung and Groundnut Shell)

Mass of Cow Dung: 04 kg

Mass of Groundnut shell: 01 kg

The volume of water used: 1000 cm³

Mass of biodigester (before adding substrate): 01 kg

Mass of biodigester (after adding substrate): 07 kg

Amount of yeast added: 0.03 kg

Temperature: 31°C

pH level: 6.62

Retention time: 7 days

TABLE 3: Bio-Digester C Measurements (Cow Dung and Groundnut Shell)

S/N	Days	pH level	Temperature (°C)	Biogas produced (cm ³)	M ₁ (kg)	M ₂ (kg)
1	Day 1	6.61	32.4	0.8	7.80	7.00
2	Day 2	6.59	33.7	1.0	8.00	7.00
3	Day 3	6.57	35.0	1.2	8.20	7.00
4	Day 4	6.51	36.1	1.3	8.30	7.00
5	Day 5	6.48	37.7	1.4	8.40	7.00

Where M₁ = mass of biodigester before measuring biogas

M₂ = mass of biodigester after measuring biogas

Figure 3: Graphical Representation of Bio-Digester C (Cow Dung and Groundnut Shells)

DISCUSSION

The biogas volume produced shows an increasing trend over the days (from Table 1), starting at 0.5 cm³ on Day 1 and reaching 0.8 cm³ by Day 5. This increase indicates that the microorganisms responsible for biogas production were becoming more active or efficient as the digestion process progressed. The gradual increase in biogas yield

was due to the microorganisms adapting to the conditions within the bio-digester over time, leading to improved digestion and gas production.

The pH values recorded are relatively stable across the days, ranging from 6.90 to 7.08. This suggests that the environment within the bio-digester remained within a neutral pH range, which is generally favorable for anaerobic digestion.

The temperature readings show slight variations, ranging from 32.1°C to 34.1°C. This temperature range aligns well with mesophilic conditions (20-40°C), which are common for biogas production. This is similar to the result obtained in the studies conducted by Adesina et al. (2024), Akpan et al. (2022), and Kusmiyati et al. (2023).

The mass measurements before and after measuring biogas (M₁ and M₂) indicate slight variations but are relatively consistent across the days. This minor change suggested that the

substrate in the bio-digester is decomposing slowly, with a small amount of material being converted to biogas. The minimal decrease in mass aligns with the gradual increase in biogas production.

From Table 2, the biogas volume steadily increases each day, beginning at 0.8 cm³ on Day 1 and reaching 1.0 cm³ by Day 5. This indicates that the microbial community is adapting to the environment and becoming more efficient in digesting the organic material and producing biogas. The steady increase suggests a healthy bio-digester environment, with microorganisms effectively decomposing the substrate to produce biogas over time.

The pH levels for Bio-digester B in Table 2 show a slight decrease over the days, starting at 6.18 on Day 1 and reaching 6.06 by Day 5. This slight decrease indicates that the bio-digesters' environment may become slightly more acidic over time. A pH below 7 is still within an acceptable range for biogas production, but if it continues to drop, it could hinder microbial activity. The gradual decrease might suggest microbial activity produces acidic byproducts, which is expected in the initial stages of anaerobic digestion.

The temperature gradually increases over the days, starting from 33.5°C on Day 1 and reaching 37.1°C by Day 5. These temperatures are within the upper end of the mesophilic range, which is suitable for anaerobic digestion. The increase in temperature could stimulate microbial activity,

potentially leading to higher biogas production. However, if the temperature rises, it might lead to thermophilic conditions, which could alter microbial populations and affect biogas production rates.

The mass readings before and after measuring biogas (M₁ and M₂) show slight variations, with M₁ slightly increasing from 7.10 kg on Day 1 to 7.15 kg on Day 5 and M₂ showing a slight increase. These small changes indicate a consistent substrate consumption rate, as only a tiny amount of material is converted to biogas daily. This aligns with the incremental increase in biogas volume observed. Bio-digester B operates effectively, with favorable conditions supporting increasing biogas yield.

Table 3 shows that biogas production increases from 0.8 cm³ on Day 1 to 1.4 cm³ on Day 5. This steady increase suggests that the biodegester is progressively stabilising and may reach optimal gas production conditions.

The pH levels gradually decreased over the five days, starting from 6.61 on Day 1 to 6.48 on Day 5. This trend may indicate an increase in acidity, which could affect the microbial activity inside the biodegester.

The temperature increases daily, from 32.4°C on Day 1 to 37.7°C on Day 5. Higher temperatures could enhance biogas production up to an optimal point, as microbial activity typically increases with temperature.

Table 3 includes two mass measurements, M_1 and M_2 , where M_1 is the mass before measuring biogas, and M_2 is the mass after. M_1 slightly increases over time, possibly indicating an accumulation of organic material or a reaction by-product. M_2 , however, remains relatively stable, with minor fluctuations, suggesting a controlled environment in terms of mass loss or biogas extraction. This is similar to the result obtained in studies conducted by Babatunde et al. (2022), Chavan et al. (2021), San et al. (2024), and Hassan et al. (2022) in their studies.

TABLE 4: Summary of All Results

S/N	Bio-digester	pH level	Temperature (°C)	Biogas produced (cm ³)
1	A	5.79	35.56	0.64
2	B	6.12	33.98	0.84
3	C	6.55	34.98	1.14

CONCLUSION

This study investigates the feasibility of using agricultural waste to produce biogas, a renewable energy source. It primarily explores the potential of Cow Dung, Neem seed, and Groundnut shell as substrates for biogas production.

Table 4 summarises key measurements from three different bio-digesters (A, B, and C) under specific pH, temperature, and biogas production conditions.

Bio-digester A has the lowest pH at 5.79, indicating more acidic conditions. Bio-digester B has a pH of 6.12, closer to neutral but slightly acidic. Bio-digester C has the highest pH at 6.55, making it the least acidic among the three. Generally, microbial activity for biogas production performs better in near-neutral pH conditions, so Bio-digester C's pH could be advantageous.

Bio-digester A is at 35.56°C, B at 33.98°C, and C at 34.98°C. The temperatures are pretty close, within a few degrees of each other. However, bio-digester A has the highest temperature, which could be beneficial as increased temperatures (up to an optimal point) enhance microbial activity and gas production.

Bio-digester A produces 0.64 cm³, B produces 0.84 cm³, and C produces 1.14 cm³. Bio-digester C has the highest biogas output, followed by B and A. This trend suggests that Bio-digester C's combination of higher pH and near-optimal temperature may be more effective for gas production.

Bio-digester C performed best in biogas output due to its higher pH (closer to neutral) and temperature, supporting microbial activity. Bio-digester A, with the lowest pH and highest temperature, produces the least biogas, which may indicate that acidity inhibits microbial efficiency despite the warm temperature. This is similar to the results obtained in studies conducted by Horváth et al. (2016), Rastogi et al. (2021), and Perveen (2024) in their studies.

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